

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable D4.6

Report on new local
baseline data on the
marine climate and
noisescape

Version 1.1

August 25, 2025

101003472 | Arctic PASSION

ARCTIC
PASSION

Work package 4

Innovating user-driven Arctic
EuroGEO Pilot Services

Lead beneficiary

GINR

Authors

Malene Simon Hegelund (GINR)

Steffen Malskær Olsen (DMI)

Partner contributors

Anna Pedersen (DMI)

Ilana Schiller Weiss (DMI)

Carl Bror Isaksen (GINR)

Else Ostermann (GINR)

Aksel Ascanius (DMI)

Julie Sofie Larsen (GINR)

Status

Final

Dissemination level

Public

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1. Executive summary

The Arctic is experiencing fast changes from the effects of global warming. While the rapidly decreasing sea ice reshapes the lives of local and Indigenous communities, it also affects the environment and habitats of sensitive marine mammals like narwhals, an important hunting animal for high Arctic communities. Arctic PASSION aims to develop a coherent and sustainable Arctic observing system that integrates scientific measurements with Indigenous and local knowledge, addressing current gaps in observation networks, improving data accessibility, and providing practical services. The project supports both local and global decision-making in response to rapid Arctic climate change.

Within the framework of the project, we designed and implemented a marine monitoring program with members of the communities in Northwest Greenland. The monitoring locations were pinpointed based on Indigenous and local knowledge, instrumentation options and data needs considered jointly with scientists. In particular, the deployment and recovery procedures for scientific equipment through sea ice were developed in a co-creation process between Indigenous expertise and western scientific methods. The Pilot Service 7 has built capacity for both Indigenous hunters and western scientists by exchanging knowledge and training one another, laying the ground for a long-term adaptive and sustainable community-endorsed monitoring program. The program will need to mature and expand in a future co-creating

process to address the full spectrum of data needs in a changing environment with multiple external stressors.

By following our protocol and the recommendations of the Pikialasorsuaq Commission and ICC, the Pilot Service has created a community-based monitoring program with tangible outputs including several information videos, an educational animation, and a biannually updated Visual Atlas. These tools aim to empower the local community with the data needed for managing their marine resources and understanding climate drivers and change.

2. Introduction

Qaanaaq, located at about 77°30' N in northwestern Greenland, is one of the world's northernmost inhabited towns, with around 620 residents. It serves as the main town for several small surrounding settlements (Siorapaluk, Qeqertat and Savissivik) and belongs to the Avannaata Municipality. The community is part of the Inughuit culture, and most people also speak Kalaallisut (Greenlandic) but the main spoken dialect is Inuktun. Qaanaaq's hunting culture remains central to daily life and identity. Hunting seals, walruses, narwhals, and fish is not only a means of survival but also a way of preserving traditions passed down for centuries. The kayak (qajaq) is still used in summer for narwhal hunting, while dog sleds are essential for winter travel and transport across the sea ice. Skills in navigation, animal preparation, and sharing resources are deeply rooted in the community's values. The town has a school with about 120 pupils, a kindergarten, and a small hospital offering basic healthcare. Qaanaaq is connected to the outside world via the Qaanaaq Airport, with scheduled flights twice a week but very irregular in practice where cancelations are the norm. Ticket prices are so high that even going to the capital Nuuk in south Greenland is not possible for many residents. The city and community is resupplied only in July and August by ship. Within the district, residents rely on dog sleds, snowmobiles, kayaks, or boats depending on the season. The area experiences increasing activities from international science teams and tourists. Especially cruise ship tourism is expanding fast. These activities are poorly regulated despite the disturbance they cause to the hunting animals, traditional hunting culture and daily life. They also put pressure on the limited logistics including the domestic flights and other services in town. Qaanaaq has a well-functioning mobile network but bandwidth is extremely limited and flat-rate services only in recent years offered with strong restrictions. Only one of the smaller settlements is connected. In this setting, it is of the utmost importance that scientific activities including climate monitoring build on local capacity, focus on identified data needs and if possible, contribute to the local economy and capacity building.

Marine mammals are an important subsistence resource for High Arctic Greenlandic communities. They are vocal animals, depending on sound for vital processes such as prey capture, finding mates and navigation. Reduction in sea ice and the increase of marine noise from ships, offshore (and coastal) development and military activities are exposing Arctic marine mammals to unprecedented levels of acoustic noise, the effects of which are a growing concern. This community-led Pilot Service 7 has provided access to information from combined sustained monitoring of the marine climate and soundscape (bioacoustics, ocean stratification) by building a community-based monitoring program in Qaanaaq. There is a critical lack of baseline data on the marine climate and noiscape, including the presence of marine mammals as highlighted by the working groups under the Arctic Council, PAME and AMAP. There has been multiple scientific activities, but to date no continued monitoring delivering a product or outputs, that the community can expect to rely on for managing their environment and living resources.

A key priority was to generate a service of local value, through inclusive decision-making and knowledge exchange that responded to both local and scientific data needs. The service created bi-directional learning between local hunters and scientists and between younger and older generations of hunters. In this co-creating environment of the Pilot Service, we have integrated Indigenous and local knowledge through community meetings and collaborative activities. We have developed a Visual Atlas (Appendix “Community-Based Marine Climate Monitoring, Qaanaaq 2025”) of annual recordings and marine activities that will be used as a dynamic tool to empower the local communities to manage their environment and to advance a dialogue on sustainable pathways for marine activities. The Visual Atlas will be made available in Danish and Greenlandic and is planned to be updated biannually with new data and new activities based on the community’s wishes and science needs.

The science and local partners have equipped and maintained one main station and two to four additional sites, identified by the communities, with sound recorders and oceanographic sensors. There has been a multi directional knowledge transfer within the team. From hunters to scientists Through meetings and workshops, we have trained local partners in the deployment, recovery and maintenance of scientific equipment. This capacity building empowers community members to participate in future scientific activities and better identify how science can aid in answering important community questions. The expertise also opens direct economic opportunities as science partners, taking part in the planning and execution of other scientific initiatives.

The Pilot Service aligns with the new agenda to bridge science and society put forward by the Greenland Government, the EC and different prominent voices in the organizational landscape including the Greenland Science Hub ([Arctic Hub – Making Arctic Research Accessible](#)). It is also articulated in the Inuit strategy for the future of Pikialasorsuaq (North Water Commission, [Home | ICC](#)), where this specific service delivers on key requirements by coordinating and

developing future activities that will combine community-based monitoring across the Pikialasorsuaq.

3. Community engagement

Community engagement is a process that requires different types of communication and activities. Through this pilot service, we have built an experienced local team executing the monitoring program in collaboration or dialogue with GINR and DMI, consisting of community members across three generations. To do so, we have as a team conducted a series of different information and engagement activities with the broader community. We exchange knowledge and experiences to plan and execute the best possible science/monitoring.

The type of community engagement activities we carried out during the project are *General community talks, School visits, Family dialogues, Training sessions, Field planning and activities, evaluations of results and activities.*

General community talks: Talks where the whole community is invited have proved important for providing the whole community with an insight into the activities, receiving results of earlier studies that can be important for their daily lives. It is also a very important forum to receive general observations of the environment, understand community concerns for activities in the area and discuss community needs for scientific data.

School visits: Talks in the school have an educational aim, to reach the children and teach them biology and oceanography, related to their lives and local environment. Through the children, information and discussions are brought into the families as well.

Family dialogues: We have had dialogues, as informal conversations over coffee, with the hunter's family in their home or our place. We get the women's opinion on the activities and on the concerns, and scientific questions. This is a more intimate conversation and can be extremely fruitful in understanding the hunting families' observations, concerns and wishes.

Training sessions: Training sessions have been conducted during the Pilot service in small groups of 2-3 hunters, visiting the research station in Qaanaaq and getting a hands-on training on how to use an instrument or how the instruments work. The training continues in the field on how to prepare the instruments for deployment and tie them together in a secure way.

Field planning and activities, evaluations of results and activities: Groups of local hunters, experienced and younger, sometimes with their wives and children. We outline the objectives of the activities together and plan how best to execute them. We listen to each other's concerns and priorities, such as instrument limitations, measurement timing, and the scheduling of local activities, to avoid disturbance.

Example of output from community dialogue 2023 - concerns and feedback

- Immediate need for better information about science activities in the area
- Instrument interference with hunting, wildlife and long-line fishing
- Impact on narwhal quotas
- Unexplained massive fish kill
- Ocean bathymetry

Example of activities during a training and capacity-building session

- Familiarize with state-of-the-art mooring equipment

- Servicing instruments and testing functionalities
- Preparing and configuring for ocean deployments

4. In situ ocean climate data

Winter monitoring of ocean physical conditions was initiated by DMI in 2011, engaging with the local community. These pilot activities have been consolidated and extended as part of the development of the Arctic Passion Pilot Service 7 activity. This includes integration with field activities related to passive acoustic monitoring (PAM). Data series for some seasons, locations and physical parameters consequently extend back 15 years and have been chosen as the baseline data for the first version of the Visual Atlas (Appendix).

Monitoring builds on the use of state-of-the-art instrumentation integrated with local hunting and fishing activities using dog sledges and small boats. The backbone instrument in the ocean program is the CTD (Conductivity, Temperature and Depth) profiler, capable of measuring the key parameters describing the oceanic conditions at high precision from the surface to the deepest parts of the fjord, reaching beyond 900m. The system used in the program includes a modular and portable electric winch that can be easily assembled by the hunters and transported on sledges, a Seabird SBE19plusV2 CTD equipped with turbidity, fluorescence and oxygen auxiliary sensors, a generator and ice augers fitting the dimensions and specifications of the CTD instrumentation. The suite of auxiliary sensors chosen for the CTD serves both local and scientific data needs but adds a level of complexity as these sensors need to be handled with additional finesse in the field, some even kept from freezing temperatures and needing shipping for routine calibration with the manufacturer.

A characteristic example of a late winter profile of temperature, salinity and oxygen profiles in the fjord obtained with the CTD as part of the community monitoring program is shown below. It illustrates the key oceanographic features that have been discussed with the community and will be displayed in the Visual Atlas:

1. The reach of the cold winter layer, which describes the upper conditions during a large part of the year and has local and remote contributions. It includes surface and polar waters formed locally or through exchange with the North Water Polynya winter layer outside the fjord.
 - a. The evolution of this layer is key to understanding the conditions under which sea ice forms.
2. The temperature maximum at depth linked to the influx of warm waters of Atlantic origin below the lighter polar waters. This layer is known to be present year-round at 300-350m depth, but temperatures exhibit strong multiannual variations
 - a. The ocean heat at this intermediate depth is a driver of upwelling and productivity in the fjord in part through interaction with marine terminating glaciers.
3. Bottom water temperatures in the deep fjord are influenced by episodic renewal and slow mixing.
 - a. Both halibut and narwhal are also found at these depths.

The Visual Atlas (Appendix) presents both the direct temperature profiles measured from each winter 2011-2025 using color coding, but most importantly, it distils the data into time-series of the above key co-designed indicators of the marine climate of the fjord. In addition to the indicators 1-3, the Atlas includes measured sea-ice and snow depth data obtained along with the CTD profiles. The Atlas offers a short introduction, a discussion, and an explanation of the main variability in the records over time.

Figure 3: Combined profiles of temperature, salinity and oxygen illustrating the key features of the layered water column in the Inglefield fjord.

The Atlas includes an example of how to combine physical ocean climate indicators with socioeconomic records, here the reported catch of Halibut compared with the indicator of the evolution of ocean temperature (Figure 4). This product is not intended to be scientifically conclusive but designed to support ongoing dialogues in the community on the impacts of climate and environmental changes. It also touches on the issues of sustainable management of marine living resources.

Figure 4: Combined records of halibut catch (blue bars) and the indicator of the temperature evolution in the warm layer 300-350m of Atlantic derived waters in the fjord (red). The dashed red line shows the shifted temperature record by 4 years suggesting a minimum response time of the adult halibut stock.

5. Passive acoustic monitoring

The decreasing sea-ice in the Arctic will open geographical areas to traffic and other human activities, which will raise the ambient noise level of the Arctic Ocean and fjords. As marine mammals are sound-sensitive and acoustic intelligent creatures, this has sparked an increasing concern for the marine mammals and the people who hunt them. The use of Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) is a method widely used to non-invasively monitor the acoustic environment and describe the underwater soundscape using a sound recorder that captures all acoustic signals in the sea at a distance, depending on the frequency and sound level. The non-invasiveness of the method is key to not disturbing the marine mammals or the hunt on them.

The acoustic component started in 2022 and in the Visual Atlas we have provided short timelines and examples of data. In the future Visual Atlas, we will provide timelines for narwhal arrival to the summer hunting ground and the dependence on the sea ice, as well as timelines for noise levels in the fjord.

Figure 5. Deployment of bottom moored instruments, through a hole in the sea ice.

A limitation to PAM recorders in the cold environment of the Arctic sea is battery longevity. To make sure our data collection covers all the year, we have developed a two-year deployment program, with deployment of bottom moored instruments through the sea ice, in spring (March-April) and a recovery of all instruments in the open-water season (August-October). After downloading and servicing all instruments, some are redeployed to record during the fall/winter period. This cycle continues on a yearly basis.

We have identified a main station in the fjord (Mooring 4 and 5 on map). From that station, we are deploying an additional array of recorders, depending on the questions we want to answer.

Figure 6. Map of Inglefield Bredning, Northwest Greenland, showing the locations of the five moorings (Moorings 1-5) used in this study. Bathymetric contours are included to illustrate seafloor topography. The inset highlights the region's location in Greenland. On the left, a schematic of mooring designs used in the study is shown.

Analysis of narwhal detections and ambient noise levels. The data shows that the narwhals do not only arrive after the sea ice has broken up, as was expected, but narwhals show a strong connection to the sea ice edge. Why they choose to remain near the ice edge, where the hunt is also most intense, is biologically interesting and points to the narwhals may be attracted to a food source in the sea ice, which outweighs the risk of the hunt. These questions have arisen from these datasets and will be investigated in the future.

Figure 7. Example of narwhal detections from acoustics over an annual cycle (orange dots) and distance to the sea ice edge (blue line) for moorings 7 and 8. Most detections occurred when the ice edge was close to the moorings or when it was ice-free, suggesting a seasonal link between sea ice conditions and narwhal presence.

The ambient noise levels showed a strong seasonal variation in ambient noise levels following the sea ice seasons (Figure 8). The sea ice dampens the ambient noise from wind, rain and melting icebergs. It also keeps traffic and air-breathing animals, such as narwhals, locked out of the fjord.

When the sea ice breaks up, there is a strong rise in the ambient noise due to small boats, wind, and vocalizing animals, especially narwhals and bearded seals. As the monitoring has only just started, we need a longer dataset for detecting trends. But data has been presented in the Visual Atlas on narwhal arrival relative to sea ice and dates for narwhal arrival in the fjord.

The impact of a sound source on marine mammals depends on the frequencies, sound levels, origin and behavioral state of the receiving animal. The variation in frequencies of sound sources relative to animal hearing (Figure 9) has been presented in the Visual Atlas (Appendix).

Figure 8. Annual variation in median noise level recorded at: A) moorings 4 and 5 combined, B) mooring 1, C) mooring 2, D) mooring 3, E) mooring 4, and F) mooring 5, plotted in a circular calendar format with daily resolution. Each plot represents the duration of available data for a given station, with frequency increasing radially outward from 10 Hz to 80 kHz. Color intensity indicates relative amplitude. Periods of fast ice are shown as solid, red lines, and drift ice as jagged, red lines, based on sea ice charts from DMI (https://ocean.dmi.dk/arctic/icecharts_gl_northwest.php).

Figure 9. Illustration of frequencies produced by different anthropogenic sound sources and the hearing of three different types of marine mammals.

6. Collaborations

Collaborations with other tasks/WP

The activity has interacted with and contributed to WP1 activities, including direct support to Fiducial Reference Measurements for surface temperature (D1.6, WP1) and dialogues across WP4 on co-creating community monitoring and with inspiration from activities around the event database (Task 4.1, WP4). The task contributes to the communication and exploitation activities across WP6 and WP9 and the project engagement with GEOS, SAON and the Arctic Council (e.g. D4.7, WP7).

External collaborations

The Pilot Service 7 has developed a network of external collaborations in the local communities of NW Greenland (Siorapaluk, Savissivik and Qaanaaq), in collaboration with stakeholder

institutions in Greenland (Arctic HUB, ICC, KNAPK and Pikialasorsuaq project, Greenland government), with Canadian communities in Pikialasorsuaq (Ajuittuq, (Grise Fiord) CBM) and with international agencies (AAON, CBMP, Baffin Bay DBO).

7. Perspectives

Establishing relationships and building trust is a gradual process, and this collaboration fundamentally relies on both. Engagement to date has included community members across a range of age groups; however, involving younger hunters has presented particular challenges. Addressing this issue will be a key focus moving forward, in partnership with older community members who have expressed a strong interest in capacity building and in transmitting knowledge to younger generations. Discussions with the school principal have further highlighted opportunities to integrate natural science curricula into ongoing monitoring initiatives through collaborative projects. To sustain these long-term, locally adapted efforts, we have identified the establishment of a community-driven knowledge hub as a critical anchor for future activities and for the systematic preservation of local knowledge.

Pikialasorsuaq is a focus area in the Greenland political arena, but it is widely acknowledged to be challenging and resource-intensive to build and keep close long term collaborative ties within the high Arctic communities in the remote region. The PS7 has been welcomed by Greenlandic stakeholders as a platform and an example of good practice of co-development of a monitoring activity building on western and indigenous science and local knowledge. We have had meetings and consultations with Greenlandic Stakeholders such as the Greenlandic hunters' organization (KNAPK), Arctic HUB ([Arctic Hub – Making Arctic Research Accessible](#)) and the Pikialasorsuaq Project (ICC and the Ministry of Environment, Greenland Government) and found that the PS7 activities fit well in the agendas and strategies of the stakeholders. We are planning future stronger links and collaborations to attach the future PS7 activities to the Arctic HUB platform and Pikialasorsuaq project's outputs.

Communities within the Pikialasorsuaq, share family ties across Greenland-Canada borders. Communities on both sides of the border have a high interest in more cross-border contact for experience- and knowledge-sharing. The Pilot Service 7 has developed contacts to Community-Based Monitoring programs in Ajuittuq (Grise Fiord community) an Indigenous community located on the Nunavut side of the Pikialasorsuaq. The community programs are developing future activities, workshops and meetings to build a closer future collaboration. Next common activities are planned for the Arctic Circle Assembly 2025 and the Greenland Science Week 2025.

PS7 has been integrated into two new international science observatories. The passive acoustic monitoring, one core part of the PS7 activities and community program has been included in the Arctic Acoustic Observation Network, linked to the CBMP Marine Mammal specialist group under the Arctic Council. We will ensure that the PAM monitoring in the PS7 will follow the guidelines, recommendations, and data storage protocols developed within the AAON framework.

The PS7 community-based monitoring program has become a key stone in the High Arctic part of the Baffin Bay DBO. The program is recognized as a DBO site by linking to Ajuittuq community, it links the Baffin Bay DBO on a community and scientific level across the Pikialasorsuaq. This work is in progress.

Continuing the production of the Visual Atlas will in part be ensured by these initiatives and also be a priority for GINR and DMI.

8. Impact and exploitation

The Visual Atlas (Appendix) will be distributed as hard copies to the communities and Greenland stakeholder organizations. It will also be uploaded as Pdf files on the webpage of Arctic Passion and the Greenland Climate Research Centre and the link will be distributed on the community Facebook page. The work of the Arctic Passion PS7 has led to several outreach, political involvement and scientific output.

Five informational videos available in English, Danish and Greenlandic explain the collaboration and methods of the work in PS7.

- <https://youtu.be/qABbVFSB5I0>
- <https://youtu.be/1aVzmGDKi7U>
- <https://youtu.be/WDUgmotKz0g>
- https://youtu.be/93q7sc4v_i8
- <https://youtu.be/7OrWvxZbrZs>

Educational animation about underwater sound.

- Under development. Will be uploaded to the GINR webpage when finished (<https://natur.gl/videoer-2/?lang=en>).

Policy involvement in Greenland and the western science community working in Greenland.

- Panel discussion at the Greenland Science Week 2023. Arctic Passion PS7 leads, Malene Simon Hegelund (GINR) and Steffen Malskær Olsen (DMI) and their collaborative partners from Savissivik Naduk Kristensen and Olennguaq Kristensen participated in a panel discussion about the impact of science on Indigenous communities and how to develop community-based research in an ethical manner.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KGHDXJ2r0a4>
- Invitation by Polar Dialogue, Arctic Circle to prepare a Plenary Session for Arctic Circle Assembly 2025 on *The impact of science on Indigenous communities and how to develop community-based research in an ethical manner*.
- Workshop in collaboration with Ajuittuq CBM at the Greenland Science Week.

Scientific output and education.

- MSc Thesis: *Seasonal Soundscapes and Narwhal presence in a changing Arctic* by Julie S Larsen, University of Aarhus, Denmark.
- Two scientific manuscripts in preparation to be submitted to scientific journals.
- Contribution to PhD thesis: 'Decadal climate variability and predictability in the North Atlantic Ocean' by Anna Pedersen (Southern Danish University and Danish Meteorological Institute). Draft paper integrating CBM data from PS7: 'Observed seasonality in carbon fixation in a high arctic fjord' (Pedersen, Löscher and Olsen, in prep 2025)

Figure 9. Panel discussion at Greenland Science Week 2023. Arctic Passion PS7 leads, Malene Simon Hegelund (GINR) and Steffen Malskær Olsen (DMI) and collaborative partners from Savissivik Naduk Kristensen and Olennguaq Kristensen.

APPENDIX

Visual Atlas "Community-Based Marine Climate Monitoring, Qaanaaq 2025".

